

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.4.3
Deliverable title	6-monthly financial report #3
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
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Deliverable due date	2020-06-30
Deliverable latest review date	2020-09-24

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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project financial progress during the reporting period ranging from 2020-01-01 to 2020-06-30, also termed in the following RP3. Please note that full reporting information is declared on SIU and the present report just represents an overview of its key contents.

Moreover, the report does not take into account possible modifications to the present conditions, which may rise during the work of the FLCs.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which is found at:

<https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect. 2.1), and Unforeseen Issues (Sect. 2.2).

2.1 General achievements

Expenditures for RP3 were reported in SIU by LP-CMCC, PP2-CSA and PP3-UniZd, considering the main activities performed during the period. Due to the COVID-19 outbreak in whole Europe in February/March 2020, travelling was inhibited by the curfew measures and expenditures of partners were mainly related to staff costs. No travel was performed and only limited external costs (i.e. FLC) and equipment could be claimed.

Notwithstanding the COVID-19 situation, with respect to the AF financial planning and later minor changes, expenditures are generally occurring in a regular manner during RP3. Exception remains for PP4-MMPI and PP5-AdSP, which do not report any costs in this reporting period, as occurred in the previous two ones.

Small adjustments of PP2-CSA budget are reported in the RP3 documentation for minor changes.

The overall financial progress, both at WP, activities and budget line levels, is summarized in Fig.1-3.

Figure 1: Financial implementation status of GUTTA WPs. Blue is the absorbed fraction of the budget, cumulative of the first three RPs; orange is the cumulative missing fraction within the current RP, and grey is the remaining fraction until the end of the project.

The WP-breakdown (Fig.1) highlights an absorption gap in WP3, despite the fact this WP could finalize its technical activities. This is mainly due to the staff costs not claimed by PP4-MMPI and PP5-AdSP. Such an unspent budget will be redistributed to the other activities of the project to be performed in the next reporting periods. Part of the underspending is related to some activities restrictions caused by COVID-19 pandemic.

The overall implementation rate, defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption, is 74.8%.

Figure 2: Financial implementation status of GUTTA activities for WPs 1 to 4. Color codes as in Fig.1

Figure 2 reports the cost breakdown at the level of project activities in the different WPs, except WP5 that has not started yet. For A1.1 and A2.2, which are the starting activities of management and communication WPs respectively, the technical work was concluded, but some budget was left unspent (i.e. the part of PP4-MMPI and PP5-AdSP). This remaining budget will be redistributed to the activities to be performed in the next reporting periods. A similar consideration can be done for the activities of WP3, as explained above. For the other activities, the spending trend generally follows the technical developments of the project.

The breakdown of the financial absorption into budget lines (Fig.3) shows underspending in this reporting period especially in the lines of travel & accommodation and external expertise. This is justified by the cancellation of physical meetings due to the ongoing pandemic, and also to the unspent amount for technical and logistic assistance in view of the second SC meeting, initially planned to occur in Bari and to be organized by PP5-AdSP.

Figure 3: Breakdown of financial implementation status of GUTTA through budget lines. Color codes as in Fig.1

2.2 Unforeseen issues

2.2.1 CMCC

- No issues

2.2.2 CSA

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in this RP documentation.

2.2.3 UniZd

- No issues

2.2.4 MMPI

- No costs were claimed in RP3, despite activities were performed and reported.

2.2.5 AdSP

- No costs were claimed in RP3, despite activities were performed and reported.

3. Conclusions

As in previous reporting periods, the financial absorption of GUTTA project in RP3 was lower than expected mainly due to the persistence of no expenses claimed by PP4-MMPI and PP5-AdSP, as well as difficulties brought by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Therefore, pending issues for upcoming RP4 include:

- Finalization of appointment of a FLC by PP5-AdSP, in order to start expenses reporting;
- Major amendment for technical activities that will also cause a redistribution of partners budget. Moreover, the budget redistribution will take into account the request of 12-months prolongation of the project duration for which GUTTA applied on September 8th 2020.